

Protection, Control & Enforcement of Laws in India Regarding the Right to Privacy and Data Protection in the Digital Age

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Abstract

Technological progress has been immensely beneficial to humanity. But more and more, our rights are being threatened by technological progress. The importance of protecting one's privacy is growing as the new economy relies on data collected and transferred more regularly in the digital era. As a result of technology improvements, new types of criminal activities have evolved, including online victimization, identity theft, and pestering. There are several potential points of exploitation for personally identifiable information that people provide online, including social media, marketing, communication monitoring companies, public and private stakeholders, and other websites. There is no specific legislation in India that controls the collection, storage, retrieval, analysis, use, or retention of data. This study sets out to look into issues related to data analysis and the right to privacy in the modern digital age. In order to learn more about privacy concerns, this research looks at scenarios where individuals' data can be used for malicious purposes, sometimes even against them. The research also makes an effort to look at how effective the Information Technology Act and other privacy rules are, and how much protection they offer for data. Since both the public and private sectors gather data at the same rate, we can study and compare how the laws affect them.

Key words: Privacy, Digital, Technology, Effectiveness and Information.

Introduction

Any society's progress is mostly propelled by technological advancements. By influencing fields as diverse as medicine, communications, and finance, it has helped humanity advance socially and individually. In the 21st century, the digital revolution has swept the globe, including India. Like everywhere else, most people in India use the internet. In light of this, the "Digital India" program was recently approved by the Indian government. There have been many positive outcomes from the "Digital India" initiative, however the processing of personal data through various electronic devices and applications has put human rights, especially the right to privacy, at risk. Due to the extensive use of the internet, individuals are routinely disclosing all of their personal information in a variety of digital formats, including apps, forms, and other electronic devices. Additionally, both public and commercial sectors are continuously gathering personal data. When people fill out forms or applications for private or public services, when they shop online, when they post on social media, when they upload resumes to job boards, when they buy sim cards or phone connections, when kids use their devices for online gaming, and many more similar activities. Key pieces of personal information including complete name, address, phone number, location, and friends list are required for all of these tasks. Advertisers and organized criminals have easy access to all of this data and information, which individuals have voluntarily supplied for specific purposes; they can abuse this data and information. Not only does this necessitate data protection regulation, but it also breaches an individual's right to privacy via various electronic ways.

The Right to Personal Data Privacy and Security

An individual's "Right to Privacy" includes the freedom to be unaccompanied by others. A person can usually choose whether to let others in on their personal details. It boils down to the fundamental human freedom to speak freely within a defined community. In fact, it lets us control the amount, way, and timing of how others can utilize the pieces we choose to share, as well as choose which bits to make public. This privilege prevents third parties from disclosing any information about the individual to the public without the individual's consent. Someone might be subject to a damages action for violating someone else's right if he does this. Many international documents, including the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the 1948¹ United Nations Convention on the Protection of Children², the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights³, and the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families⁴, all acknowledge that the right to privacy is fundamental.

There is no explicit right to privacy in India, contrary to the International Instruments. Article 21⁵ of the Indian Constitution guarantees the right, which was made official by rulings in landmark cases including *R. Rajagopal v. State of Tamil Nadu*, or "Auto Shankar's Case." In this instance, Auto Shankar addressed his relationships with several IAS, IPS, and other police officials in his autobiography, which he authored while incarcerated for several murders. While he was doing crimes, some of them helped him. To prevent government officials from obstructing the publishers' right to publish the aforesaid autobiography, the editor of the Tamil magazine "Nakkeeran" filed a writ petition. Government officials do not have a right to privacy when it comes to things pertaining to their public duties, according to the Supreme Court's ruling in the case. This holds true regardless of whether the information published is true or not. Defamatory material could not be pre-emptively restricted from transmission since the State or its authorities did not have the authority to do so. Unless the publication is proven to be false, officials are powerless to do anything.

So, according to Article 21 of the Indian Constitution, one's right to privacy is closely related to one's right to life and personal liberty. Having said that, privacy is not a given in India. The following conditions must be met: it must be in the best interest of India's sovereignty and integrity; there must be a significant, superior countervailing interest; it must be in the state's interest; it cannot be granted to individuals who willingly enter into controversy; and it must be contrary to the interest of private citizens.

Now let us talk about data security. The term "data" needs to be defined before we can proceed. under the IT Act of 2000, the term "data" is defined under Section 2(1)(o). It gives us the method of data collection itself, which can be described in the following way:

Data is defined as -

- (a) a representation of data, expertise, information, ideas, or procedures;
- (b) being made ready; or
- (c) Formally prepared in a computer system or network.

Moreover, it details the many ways in which such data might be transmitted, including computer printouts, magnetic or optical storage media, punched cards, punched tapes, and even the computer's internal memory.

The growing number of internet users, the proliferation of mobile applications, and other factors have all contributed to an explosion in the quantity of data produced by India's digital push. Everyone may agree that data generation has helped people and society advance through making more efficient use of resources. Unfortunately, the data that is generated is often misused and poorly protected, which violates people's right to privacy. In a recent case, *K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India*⁶, the Supreme Court was asked to decide this very question. The "Aadhaar Card Scheme," which demanded biometric data for an identification card in order to access public services and benefits, was challenged in 2012 by retired High Court Judge Puttaswamy over its constitutionality. The Aadhaar Card Scheme is facing allegations of rights violations. The case and the validity of the Court's

rulings in *M.P. Sharma v. Satish Chandra, District Magistrate, Delhi*⁷, and *Kharak Singh v. State of Uttar Pradesh*⁸ were both ordered to be examined by a three-judge bench. A 5-judge bench first heard this case on July 18, 2017, and then referred it to a 9-judge bench. With a majority decision, the Supreme Court upheld the right to privacy under Article 21 of the Constitution, which is an essential component of the right to life and personal liberty. Therefore, the right to privacy may lead to two interrelated safeguards: one against the state and another against the general public (the ability to decide what personal information is made public). Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd) v. Union of India⁹ was decided by a nine-judge panel that was asked to determine whether the "Aadhar Card Scheme," which gathers biometric and demographic data from citizens for different reasons, infringes upon their "right to privacy."

During his remarks on the modern right to privacy and information, the Hon'ble Mr. Justice D.Y. Chandrachud elaborated on the concept of "informational privacy." He claims that in the modern information era, individuals face threats to their right to privacy from both the state and non-state actors. Therefore, he suggests that the Union Government assess and establish a robust data protection framework that finds a middle ground between legitimate state concerns and private rights before submitting such an application. He went on to say that the Union Government can't build such a strategy without taking into account the states' legitimate interests in areas like national security, crime prevention and investigation, etc., if it wants to strike this balance. In this case, the nine-judge panel reached a unanimous decision that the "Aadhaar Card Scheme" breaches people's "right to privacy" as guaranteed by Article 21 of the Indian Constitution because it does not have a robust data protection framework. While this right is guaranteed by Article 21, it must fulfil three conditions: (i) being lawful; (ii) serving a reasonable purpose; and (iii) being proportional.

Issues to be Considered

As it drafts privacy legislation, the Indian parliament should keep the following in mind.

Prevention of both official and private entities' illegal and capricious meddling— Legislators ought to make sure that nobody's right to privacy is illegally and arbitrarily taken away. Currently, existing legal precedents limit the ability of government agencies to violate citizens' private rights. Defending against governmental and private sector meddling is essential for a comprehensive law. Violations of privacy, audio/video surveillance, and communication interception are other concerns that the legal framework should handle. Further, it should work to limit or eliminate the possibility that innovative technologies will be used to violate people's right to privacy and personal information. Web cookies¹⁰, problematic payment systems, forms for Internet services, browsers, and spam email¹¹ are just a few of the many things that put people's right to privacy online at risk.

- I. **Preservation of Medical Records—**Doctors and health insurers were the principal users of patients' medical records. However, many more health practitioners and organizations now have access to medical records because of electronic records and large databases of medical data. There are legitimate worries about the possible misuse¹² of individually identifiable medical data due to the enormous number of parties that frequently have access to it, yet this accessibility does allow research that can advance understanding of diseases and treatments across broad populations. Prior to collecting and selling patient data to scientific researchers, patients must give their approval. An invasion of privacy and a violation of the duty of confidentiality due by medical practitioners to patients, tracking such data has become increasingly impossible with the emergence of the internet. Nevertheless, any measure implemented in this area cannot be deemed illegal under Article 47¹³ if it serves the public interest.
- II. **Safeguarding financial data—**Strict measures are needed to prevent fraud and other criminal activities due to the increasing number of fraud cases. It is crucial to ensure that individuals' financial records are not shared or transferred among financial institutions without their knowledge or consent, unless required to do so by law. Such sharing or transfer could lead to

crimes like kidnapping or extortion, among others, and could compromise an individual's right to privacy.

- III. Preventing employers from overly monitoring their staff** - Another major concern, especially for the working class, is the widespread practice of invasive corporate spying. We need to take a holistic approach to this issue, which is becoming more essential. Earlier, we established that this relates to personally identifiable information. Electronic "eyeballs" are responsible for this. Businesses justify their use of this technology by saying it helps them work more efficiently. In contrast, Stair makes a point of highlighting the ethical dilemma that comes with using this technology in his defence of this activity. These technologies, in his view, invade people's privacy while they are on the job. The so-called panopticon phenomenon, in which people always feel watched, can also be exacerbated by this.¹⁴

Information Security and the Materiality of Information Technology:

Security, moral, and regulatory issues are all brought up by particular, concise aspects of innovations. An exploitative "access-for-information" arrangement is the bedrock of the worldwide reconnaissance administration and the promotion-based paradigm of the Internet. Customers can get free data and correspondence services online as they wastefully use all their own data. Different levels of protection are controlled by different stages, and access to customer information is ensured by different conditions of administration. There is a significant risk of possible information and fraud, as well as terrible client reconnaissance, since all 26 of the security applications for ladies require protection procedures or limits of use. With each new piece of technological innovation that permeates our society, we are prompted to reevaluate the physical framework of security. Working together, Deep Mind and the UK's National Health Service show that unified data frameworks are susceptible to breaches, data insurance rules and use limitation laws notwithstanding. Through the use of indirect access methods, individual advanced colleagues have been able to transmit recorded discussions back to equipment producers. Thanks to smart data and Internet of Things advances, devices can connect with each other without human intervention, allowing home delivery automatons to scour consumers' houses for potential buying opportunities. The 'notice and gathering' guideline and other earlier protection protocols are now obsolete in this data age. The rational debate on the fundamental idea of security is likewise poised to reach new heights thanks to the strict code of technical advancements. Social profiling and the exclusion of underutilized network members are becoming more likely as a result of advances in Big Data analysis made possible by subjective figuring. "The sheer number and lavishness of databases and the expanding advancement of calculations" puts entire social gatherings at risk of educational insecurity, according to some experts, and it also leaves individuals vulnerable to governmental and corporate surveillance. At this point in time, there are no rules that control computations or AI. Instead of viewing security as a discrete right, it should be considered as a PDF. The present Aadhaar-based system, which employs ID numbers to trace customers of an increasing number of taxpayer-supported organizations, strips individuals of control over their own unique biometric data in the specific decisions of techno-plan to disperse impoverished apportions through biometric check. The reality is that it leaves them vulnerable to widespread fraud, as shown in multiple news reports around the country. It was absolutely doable to select a less centralised system using smart cards (PDF), with each recipient keeping their own record of data, as mentioned earlier. But the civil argument is occasionally made to look like a done deal: being poor definitely means giving up the luxury of security.

Conclusion

One of the most important foundations of personal liberty and dignity is the right to privacy. Today's modern society is defined by a pervasive social culture and easy access to the internet, making it more important than ever to protect one's personal privacy. The widespread use of social media and digital platforms has made people more susceptible to data exploitation and privacy violations. As a result, in the digital age, it is crucial for people to continue being watchful and proactive in protecting their privacy. It takes deliberate measures and conscious effort to maintain privacy in the digital sphere. To

safeguard their personal information, people need to exercise caution when using the internet and take the appropriate safety measures. Improving internet security and privacy can be achieved with very easy actions like emptying cookies, not keeping passwords, and routinely scanning devices for unwanted access. Furthermore, people must proceed with caution when communicating with unfamiliar callers or texts. Hackers frequently use phishing techniques, in which they pose as trustworthy organizations in order to obtain private information, to take advantage of gullible people. To reduce the chance of being a victim of a cyber-attack, it is crucial to avoid opening attachments from unknown sources or clicking on dubious links. People should also exercise caution when disclosing personal information online, such as their daily schedules and physical locations. People who overshare personal information on social media can become targets of identity theft, cyberbullying, and stalking, among other dangers. In order to restrict access to personal information, it is advised to examine and tighten privacy settings on social media profiles. Privacy is important for more reasons than just safeguarding personal information. It includes components of human life such as personality development, human dignity, safety, and willpower. People have the ability to express themselves freely in private without worrying about being judged or having their privacy violated. It gives people a sense of empowerment and security that makes it possible for them to face the challenges of modern life with self-assurance and independence. On the other hand, improper use of digital and social media platforms can seriously harm people's privacy and well-being. Overexposure to internet monitoring and inspection can damage one's self-esteem and destroy personal boundaries. In order to preserve their privacy and mental health, people must therefore find a balance between using social media's advantages for connectivity and setting limits.

References:

- 1 Article 12: "No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks."
- 2 Article 16.1: "No child shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his or her privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to unlawful attacks on his or her honour and reputation."
- 3 Article 17.1: "No one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to unlawful attacks on his honour and reputation."
- 4 Article 14: "No migrant worker or member of his or her family shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his or her privacy, family, home correspondence or to other communications, or to unlawful attacks on his or her honour and reputation. Each migrant worker and member of his or her family shall have the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks."
- 5 Article 21: "No person shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty except according to the procedure established by law."
- 6 (2015) 8 SCC 735.
- 7 AIR 1954 SC 300.
- 8 AIR 1963 SC 1295.
- 9 (2017) 10 SCC 1.
- 10 An Internet Browser interprets HTML the programming language of the Internet, into the words and graphics that are seen by Internet users when viewing a web page.
- 11 Spam is the use of e-mail addresses for a purpose that consumers have not consented for and constitute a violation of personal rights.
- 12 US Report to Congressional Requesters on Medical Records Privacy", www.epic.org/privacy/medical/gaomedical-privacy399.pdf.
- 13 M. Vijaya v. Singareni Collieries Co. Ltd., AIR 2001 AP 502.
- 14 Stair, R.M. Principles of Information Systems. A Managerial Approach. Boston: Boyd & Fraser, Pg665, 1992.

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